

Advancing the Catalogue of the World's Natural History Collections

- 10 recommendations from DiSSCo

A contribution from the DiSSCo technical team in response to the questions in the idea paper for the consultation (<https://docs.gbif.org/collections-idea-paper>)

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Executive Summary

In this document the technical team discusses and provides recommendations for in particular the questions: Q1,2,3,6,7,8,9,10,14,16,17.

The 10 recommendations are in summary:

1. Make the scope for the catalogue Natural Science Collections. This allows to include earth sciences collections (Geology, mineralogy palaeontology and anthropology collections) and life sciences (representing living organisms), and puts the focus on the most important characteristics: Natural and Science.
2. Within that scope the registry should be as inclusive as possible, and allow any collection unless it clearly has not a purpose for Natural Science, Natural History or Natural Heritage.
3. Make a separation between (1) institute collections, (2) private collections, and (3) other collections, and ensure that the institute is the primary source of information for an institute collection.
4. Make a separation between a registry of organisations and a registry of collections. Natural Science organisations are not different from other research organisations and do not need a dedicated organisation registry.
5. Provide a resolvable PID for collections through the Handle system in combination with a metadata profile defined for collections metadata to become FAIR (*Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable*) (e.g. including the collection abbreviation, ROR, ORCID iDs and other relevant metadata).
6. Consider the feasibility to make collection abbreviations, widely used as labels for institute collections, globally unique.
7. Make the collection descriptions discoverable in the main search engines and other external services.
8. Make the collection descriptions machine actionable, and provide a DOIP (*Digital Object Interface Protocol*) interface.
9. Allow community contributions, roles with different authority, and provide clear ownership information and versioning.
10. Include attribution metadata through implementation of the [TDWG-RDA attribution recommendation](#).

Introduction

The DiSSCo technical team and the DiSSCo linked projects [ICEDIG](#), [SYNTHESYS+](#), [MOBILISE](#) and [DiSSCo Prepare](#) are designing and prototyping how to include data describing collections as part of the DiSSCo Research Infrastructure. In this document we intend to synthesize the ideas and results so far as a response to the questions raised for public consultation to establish a catalogue of the world's natural history/natural science collections.

Collections scope and definition

The OED defines a collection as 'A number of objects collected or gathered together, viewed as a whole; a group of things collected and arranged'. We can interpret broadly and say that any set of physical things (material/natural objects) or image, audio and video recordings (either analogue or digital) treated together for curative purposes can be considered to be a collection. Recordings can be e.g. bird sound recordings or images of lost specimens. Collections can be hierarchical, consisting of several smaller collections. Collections change over time and, especially in the digital era, things in a collection when represented digitally can belong to more than one collection simultaneously. Thus, relations exist and inferences can be made.

Our definition of a Collection:

A collection is any set of physical things (material/natural objects) or image, audio and video recordings (either analogue or digital) treated together for curative purposes.

Important to note here is that the concept of an extended specimen ([Webster, 2017](#)) conveys the current perspective of the biodiversity specimen as extending beyond the singular physical object to potentially limitless additional physical preparations and digital resources.

The idea paper suggests Natural History Collections as scope for the future global catalogue. We see the scope of GRSciColl: Global Registry of Scientific Collections (GRSciColl) as too broad (including all kinds of scientific collections, not only natural science collections). This makes it too hard to provide standardised collection description profiles. Also, the current GRSciColl includes information on the institutes that curate these collections. Having Natural History Collections as the scope may be too narrow however. DiSSCo is a distributed infrastructure for Natural Science Collections in Europe and we would like to see all our Natural Science Collections included in the global catalogue.

Figure 1: Natural Science collections vs Natural History collections?

We have been discussing the definitions of a Natural History Collection versus the definition of a Natural Science Collection to see how these are different, but were unable to clearly distinct these. It became clear however that most of the unclarity is in definition of a Natural History Collection, which according to some may include non-biological collections like mineral collections and according to some exclude part or all of the living collections. Also the term History is confusing, it is sometimes understood as "knowledge as a narrative" and sometimes as "knowledge of past events". We concluded that we find the term "Natural Science Collection" less ambiguous than the term "Natural History collection".

In the discussions it became clear that "Natural" and "Science" are the key characteristics that we find important, and it is much more evident when using the term Natural Science Collection that earth sciences collections (Geology, mineralogy palaeontology and anthropology collections) and life sciences collections (representing living organisms) which we would like to be included are in scope.

Our definition of a Natural Science Collection:

A collection is a Natural Science Collection when its items are evidence of nature's biodiversity or geodiversity and are preserved, catalogued, and managed for the purpose of scientific study

DiSSCo is a distributed infrastructure for Natural Science Collections in Europe. In DiSSCo, all collections held at the participating institutes with a value for natural science are in scope, also collections that are not earth or biodiversity artefacts like a collection of books used for natural science. These will not be described to the level of detail as specimen collections, but are included in DiSSCo services for visits, loans and digitisation on demand. DiSSCo institutes may have natural history collections that have no scientific value or are not evidence of nature and are therefore not in scope of DiSSCo.

Recommendations:

1. Make the scope for the catalogue Natural Science Collections. This allows to include earth sciences collections (Geology, mineralogy palaeontology and anthropology collection) and life sciences (representing living organisms), and puts the focus on the most important characteristics: Natural and Science.

2. Within that scope the registry should be as inclusive as possible, and allow any collection unless it has clearly not a purpose for Natural Science, Natural History or Natural Heritage.

In DiSSCo the main focus is on collections containing specimens. Note that there is no uniform definition of a specimen. In this document we also may refer to these objects as artefacts or samples without trying to make a clear distinction. To describe such collections, DiSSCo will use a richer collection description profile than for other collections. This specimen collection profile will describe what is in the collection, where it was collected, from which time period and how it is preserved. For other collections, like an archive, we may use a profile that only contains a general collection description plus access information.

For different use cases in DiSSCo we need to define a collection on different levels:

1. We need to be able to describe the sum of the specimen collections in Europe, a virtual European collection. For this we need to use a standardised vocabulary and standard way to count collection objects in the collection holdings in the different institutes, with discrete collections (a physical object/specimen can occur in only one collection). This is in particular useful for scientists.
2. Other use cases require treating the total collection holdings of an institute as one collection to provide an overview. This is in particular useful for collection managers and directors. In combination with, for example digitisation status also for funders.
3. Again, other use cases require treating a part of an institute collection holdings as one collection. This is needed if these parts have different access protocols or different reporting needs. If there are many, these may be grouped in a collection group, which may also be seen as a collection.
4. In the previous examples providing access is the main purpose for providing a collection description. The access provider (institute or private person) is responsible for providing the description. There may however also be research or history purposes to describe an aggregation of specimens as a collection. Examples: a reference collection for an environmental sampling project, a collection of all type specimens in an institute, the specimens collected in an expedition. Such a description can be provided by any person, for example a researcher or curator.

Table 1: Collection profiles overview

collection description type	profile	primary purpose	requirements
Collection holdings description	institute collection	providing access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • description owned and maintained by the institute providing access • provides a description and access information or pointers to contained collections and/or collection groups, that contain the access information
Collection group description	institute collection	providing access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • description owned and maintained by institute • provides a description and access information or pointers to contained collections, that contain the access information
Collection description	institute collection	providing access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • description owned and maintained by institute • provides a description and access information • provide pointers to datasets of digital specimen if part of the collection is digitised
Private collection holdings description	private collection	providing access	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • description owned and maintained by the person or institute providing access • provides a description and access information • provide pointers to datasets of digital specimen if part of the collection is digitised
Other collection description	collection for research, history	providing reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • description owned and maintained by creator of

	or heritage purpose	or description	the description <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • provide pointers to institute collections or datasets of digital specimen
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Note that in this overview, we propose a pointer to the digital specimen dataset DOI, which contains the metadata about the dataset, not including the digital specimen dataset itself as a bitstream of a collection description object. We do not consider details on specimen level as part of the collection registry.

In DiSSCo, the focus is on describing individual specimens. Primary use cases for describing collections are:

1. To make collection holdings discoverable. For this use case a collection holding can be described either on a collection holdings level (the total of the collection holdings at an institute) or on a collection level.
2. To describe access, like providing a loan form or providing a visiting address. This can be different for different collections within an institute. In some cases, like a herbarium, it is the same for all the material. So for a herbarium there may be only one collection as institute collection.
3. To identify gaps (e.g. taxonomic, regional) and coordinate priorities across institutions.

To be able to provide aggregation of collection information on institutional, country or international level it is required that there is no overlap between institute collections in DiSSCo: each physical specimen or object can be part of only one collection. That is why it is important to distinguish in the catalogue between institute collections and private collections versus other collection descriptions (other aggregates of specimens/objects). Institute collection descriptions should also be controlled: there should be no duplicate descriptions and the primary source for the data should be the institute itself. In ELViS (DiSSCo's European Loans and Visits System) we have envisaged a separate role within the institute to maintain the information about the institute collections (and other information like about the facilities and services): the *institute moderator* (we may find a better term in the future). For DiSSCo, CETAF may be the authority for DiSSCo to ensure that the institute records are maintained by institute moderators.

Figure 1: Initial wireframe for Institute Moderator in ELViS to add a collection.

Recommendation:

3. Make a separation between (1) institute collections, (2) private collections, and (3) other collections, and ensure that the institute is the primary source of information for an institute collection.

It is up to the institution to decide how far to go with specifying individual institute collections, however since the primary goal for an institute collection description is to describe access, a separation into collections that have the same access is not encouraged. For example to describe different taxonomic groups within a herbarium as different collections. This is not needed as the herbarium as a whole can be described using a standardised vocabulary for taxonomic groups as developed in TDWG CD.

Institutes and Datasets

Sometimes collections are confused with institutes, in particular if there is one institute collection like in a herbarium. It is not immediately clear whether a herbarium code is a code for the institute or its collection. From DiSSCo's perspective these are different. We see the institute as the organisation responsible for providing access to the collection and its preservation, not the collection itself. We recommend to separate a collection registry from a registry of organisations and to promote or require the use of an organisation identifier. Any organisation identifier could be allowed in the global registry of collections, but in DiSSCo we will use ROR or GRID (see blogpost:

<https://diissco.tech/2020/04/11/identifiers-for-our-institutes-grid-and-ror/>). If GBIF aims to maintain a registry of institutes it might be better to include all institutes that provide data to GBIF rather than only collection providers.

Recommendation:

4. Make a separation between a registry of organisations and a registry of collections. Natural Science organisations are not different from other research organisations and do not need a dedicated organisation registry.

Datasets can also be confused with collections. We see a Natural Science collection as a collection of physical objects: bones, plants, rocks or tapes with sound recordings that provide evidence of nature diversity. A dataset is a collation of digital data. When a collection is digitised however, a collection description can be distilled from the digital data about individual specimens (which provide much more detail than the description of a collection that is not digitised). The distinction is not always clear however. A dataset with digital images from observations could be seen as collection, the images provide evidence of natural diversity or biological interactions. We think however that random aggregations should be excluded, like aggregations put together for specific scientific studies, often by a single scientist who then has to go on a deposit somewhere so they can get their article published. We suggest to only accept a dataset as a collection if it meets the following (curation) characteristics:

1. the collection is a work of enduring reference and
2. it has been put together as a systematic endeavour to make it a reference point.

In other words, it should have characteristics similar to an institute collection.

Collection identifiers

In DiSSCo it is important to be able to uniquely identify a collection as we want to connect the collection information with its specimen, its collection holding institute, contributors, contributions, scholarly outputs etc.

GrBio historically supported several persistent identifier solutions, e.g. LSIDs and COOL URIs. LSIDs provided neither a global resolving mechanism nor a centralised provider registration, and the implementation of this standard is relatively complex; reasons why LSIDs became deprecated. As we can see with GrBIO/GRSciColl, solutions like COOL URIs are also not ideal since URLs do change over time. With moving an application from one host to another it quickly becomes a pain to maintain them.

Currently when creating a new collection in GRSciColl the collection does not get a persistent identifier anymore, although the GRSciColl URI or the GUID part of it can be used

as such. But there is no guarantee of persistence, nor is it fully resolvable. It provides a URI to a landing page that a human can read but there is no access for machines. It does therefore not meet the EOSC PID policy criteria, which is an issue for DiSSCo and other infrastructures in Europe. Also, it does not provide a minimum set of metadata making the PID [FAIR](#).

The only current PID systems that are capable of providing this are the Archival Resource Key (ARK) and the Handle service, although conceptually any URN-based service with a managed global resolver would be capable of doing so. ARKs have no central governance and no central resolving infrastructure. Therefore also no costs involved for assigning ARKs. These properties make them very suitable for local or temporary identifiers but less so as globally resolvable persistent identifiers. The Handle system with its Global Handle Registry under the governance of the DONA foundation is the most widely used system for persistent identifiers that are resolvable and support a kernel with basic metadata. Handles are the basis of DOIs administered by the International DOI Foundation, identifiers assigned by ePIC and by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) to give but a few examples..

Historically for natural history collections abbreviations have been used to identify them in, for example specimen labels and in literature. With the exception of herbarium identifiers these have been assigned locally, and therefore are not always unique. Making them unique would be beneficial but requires a global authority guarding their uniqueness or a mechanism like first come first served, which may not be desirable. GBIF in its role as an aggregator may not be well suited to be the global authority, collection holding institutes are not GBIF members, is not for example an association of collection holding institutes. Regional organisations like CETAF could play that role but do not exist everywhere in the world. Index Herbariorum can do it only for herbariums. There may not be that many duplicates though. It might work to just do it once in a community effort and then for new abbreviations to have a first come first served solution.

These abbreviations are labels rather than PIDs because they are not resolvable, but they should be included in the metadata of a persistent, resolvable identifier. Guidance on proper use of the abbreviation versus the identifier in e.g. literature will need work.

For creating PIDs for collections we see a few options:

- Making the current GRSciColl URIs resolvable through content negotiation. The easiest solution but this has still the drawback of fixed URIs, and the registry moved a few times already in the past!
- Using DataCite DOIs will bring the benefits of the Handle system (URIs can change without changing the PID) and the DOI system (adding Kernel metadata). GBIF already provides DOIs for datasets through DataCite. Having a new metadata schema used with DOIs through either becoming a new registration agency or asking an existing one to provide a new schema seems not feasible for the few thousand collection descriptions. It should make use of the [DataCite metadata schema](#) made for datasets as this is the best fit. However there are some issues with using this schema to describe collections, the most important ones:
 - It should be possible to tell from the PID and its metadata that this one pertains to a natural science collection and not any other kind of resource.

The only property in the DataCite schema suitable to hold this information is ResourceType and its sub-property resourceTypeGeneral. ResourceType is free text which does not offer a reliable classification. The only usable value for resourceTypeGeneral is "Other".

- Publisher and PublicationYear are mandatory in the datacite schema but have no use for collection descriptions.
- It is not obvious to put the name of a collection in Title and controlled values for Title are AlternativeTitle Subtitle TranslatedTitle, there are no values for Name, NameAlias, NameTranslated or NameAcronym. Acronyms are important for collections.

It might not prove too difficult to get the DataCite schema adapted for our needs, as these are pretty generic, not very difficult to solve and for other physical objects, like instruments (see: RDA [PIDINST](#)) the same issues apply. Some of these are already on the roadmap, see: <https://github.com/datacite/schema/issues/70> to -75 .

- Alternative to DOIs would be using [ePIC](#). ePIC has the advantage of being able to support arbitrary schemas, which makes it very flexible as a PID infrastructure for pretty much anything. The tooling around DataCite and DOIs more generally are, however, more mature. Choosing DOIs first and later changing to ePIC will be problematic as they have a different top-level prefix (10. vs .21.).

From a technical design point of view, PIDs' strings should be opaque (not have semantic meaning), and although Handles support UTF8, it would be better to restrict to ASCII characters to avoid issues with putting them in URIs for display in browsers. Since there will not be millions of collection descriptions, the strings can be short. Note that for DOIs that are both long strings and widely used, there is a [short DOI](#) service available. A checksum implementation to ensure the validity of the string would be beneficial, as e.g. implemented in ORCID iDs:

<https://support.orcid.org/hc/en-us/articles/360006897674-Structure-of-the-ORCID-Identifier>

If collection abbreviations can be made globally unique, it would be possible to include them in the identifier as the Handle suffix. That would make the PID both resolvable and readable, however then the PID string is no longer opaque. The DiSSCo technical team is divided on whether it is more important that it is opaque or that it is readable. It is clear though that only an abbreviation is not enough as it is not resolvable and that the PID will need to have the abbreviation in its metadata anyway. Also, for non-institute collections an abbreviation may not always be needed.

Recommendations:

5. Provide a resolvable PID for collections through the Handle system in combination with a metadata profile defined for collections metadata to become FAIR (*Findable*,

Accessible, Interoperable, Re-useable) (e.g. including the collection abbreviation, ROR, ORCID iDs and other relevant metadata).

6. Consider the feasibility to make collection abbreviations, widely used as labels for institute collections, globally unique.

Global Collection Registry users and usage

As a browsable online catalogue, a global collection registry does not serve many use cases. The true value of a global registry comes when the collection descriptions in the registry are machine accessible and ideally also machine actionable. Since we describe a physical set of objects, all descriptive information can be seen as metadata and all of it needs to be available for machine processing. The information can then be used in services like ELViS to provide information on loans and visits, in a service to show the digitisation status of the collections, or services that combine collection descriptions with research, usages, people etc. When combined in ELViS with digitisation requests, it can provide new incentives for digitisation requests. For this DiSSCo requires a Digital Object Interface (implementing [DOIP](#)) to the catalogue, whereby queries return Collection objects, or where specific requested operations on Collection objects lead to modifications of the catalogue registry. It would also be needed to 'tag' institute collections as being part of e.g. DiSSCo or CETAF.

The screenshot shows the ELViS interface for creating a digitisation request. At the top is a navigation bar with icons for Institutions, Requesters, Collections, Facilities, Calls, and Requests. Below this is a breadcrumb trail: ← Calls / Test. A progress indicator shows four steps: Type, Institutions & Collections (current), Impact, and Finish. The main content area is titled 'Institutions involved' and shows a list of institutions. The first institution is '1. Botanischer Garten und Botanisches Museum Berlin'. Below this, there is a form for 'Collection(s) involved' with fields for 'Collection name', 'Number of specimens to digitise', and 'Preservation type'. There is also a 'Further details' text area. On the right side, there is a 'Status of request' section with a 'Draft' button, and a 'Request by' section with fields for Name (Wouter Addink), Email (wouter.addink@naturalis.nl), and ORCID (https://orcid.org/1234-sdfs-werw-rwj). There is also a 'Comments' section.

Figure 3. Selecting collections for a digitisation request in ELViS.

To be valuable, such a catalogue would need to become the single and trusted authoritative source of collections information, avoiding any doubt as to its completeness or the need to go and consult other (also partially complete catalogues) to obtain a full picture.

For discovery most people will use google search rather than going to the catalogue. It would therefore be important to make collection descriptions discoverable in the main search engines through using schema.org and it's extension bioschemas.org. It should be possible to register new collections (individual or in batch) with the API, e.g. to register an institution collection from within the CETAF registry tool. It should also be possible to update the information.

Figure 4. Workflow between CETAF manual collection descriptions registration, DiSSCo collection objects index and services in DiSSCo providing automated collection data, and GRSciColl.

Figure 5. An overview of all collections in Europe by aggregating MICS-1 collection descriptions data.

While we see the organisation as the owner of an institute collection and principally responsible for updates (by the person(s) with institute moderator role for that institute), it is important to also allow community contributions. Whether that is in the form of enrichment/comments or updates is debatable, but it should always be clear what the authoritative version is as supplied by the institution. If the community (verified persons) are allowed to update then both the latest version as supplied by the community as well as the latest version supplied by an institute moderator as authority should be available and presented together. With e.g. Covid-19 we see that citizen scientists would be able to update and enrich the data much faster (e.g. with tagging all collections that include information on potential zoonotic reservoirs like bat species) than the institutes. Incorporating data from wikidata or other citizen science platforms would be desirable. Attribution (provenance) information should be stored to recognise what events caused an update and by who (can be both humans or machines). See the [TDWG-RDA attribution recommendation](#). Some properties, like owner of the collection description, should only be changeable by the institute, or by a trusted admin in the case the institute is no longer able to update the record and the ownership needs to change.

Being able to show versions supplied by different actors with different roles means that versions need to be stored. Also, when part of the metadata is generated from the already digitised specimen, the collection description should be updated each time there is a new version of the digitised specimen.

Recommendations:

7. Make the collection descriptions discoverable in the main search engines and other external services.

8. Make the collection descriptions machine actionable, and provide a DOIP (*Digital Object Interface Protocol*) interface.

9. Allow community contributions, roles with different authority, and provide clear ownership information and versioning.

10. Include attribution metadata through implementation of the [TDWG-RDA attribution recommendation](#).

Collection metadata needed by DiSSCo

It has not yet been defined in detail which data and metadata we need from collection descriptions for DiSSCo services. but we know some things already:

- Some services we can already provide with a minimum of information. We call this 'Minimum Information about a Collection' (MICS) level 0, Overview information (summary) about a collection. This is e.g. the identifier, name label information (name (official name for the collection in English) and alternate names: aliases, acronyms and the name in other languages (at least the official languages used in the country where the collection is kept), a text description, institute identifier (ROR).
- Some services need more detailed information in a standardised format, e.g. what, where from, when collected, how preserved, digitisation status. In DiSSCo we call this MICS level 1. We need this standardised, so TDWG CD dimensions would apply: e.g., GeoLogicalTimeRange, etc. Which dimensions depend on the type of collection, a geological collection needs GeoLogicalTimeRange but cannot be classified in organism groups. Much work in defining the different types of collections has already been done in e.g. [ICEDIG D2.3](#), SYNTHESYS+ Task 2.2 and TDWG CD.
- Some services need to link references from historical collections to their current collection or status, or need to link collections. Information like: isPartOf, isDerivedFrom, isAlternateOf, Includes.

We see the first two as something to be provided by an institute moderator (for institute collections), where it depends on the capabilities of the institute and size of the collection holdings to what level of information to provide and maintain. This may be indicated with bronze, silver, gold etc. service levels. The third one may be more something for AI implementations, specific services or citizen scientists to provide.